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Machine Learning in RPL-Based IoT Networks and Cyber Attack Detection with Deep Learning Approaches

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies has made RPL-based IoT networks increasingly vulnerable to routing attacks such as Blackhole, Version Number, and Hello Flood. This study proposes a machine learning and deep learning-based approach to effectively detect these attacks. A realistic IoT network dataset was constructed, containing key network attributes such as frame. Time (timestamps), frame.len (packet lengths), wpan.src64, and wpan.dst64 (source and destination MAC addresses), icmpv6. Type, and icmpv6.code (ICMPv6 packet types and codes), ipv6.src and ipv6.dst (IPv6 source and destination addresses), along with classification labels. The attack detection system was developed using LightGBM, XGBoost, LSTM, and BiLSTM algorithms and evaluated through performance metrics such as F1-score and AUC. BiLSTM achieved superior performance in detecting Blackhole and Hello Flood attacks by effectively analyzing sequential patterns in frame, time, and ICMPv6 features. At the same time, LightGBM demonstrated a low computational cost and fast testing times, making it highly suitable for resource-constrained IoT devices. All models provided high classification accuracy and real-time processing capability, fulfilling the early intervention needs in IoT cybersecurity. The proposed solution not only ensures robust detection of routing attacks in RPL-based IoT networks but also lays a strong foundation for enhancing the long-term security and resilience of IoT ecosystems.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) enables the interconnection of physical devices via the internet, facilitating profound transformations across various domains, from everyday life to industrial applications. In this context, the IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks (RPL) has emerged as a fundamental routing protocol for the communication of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in Low-Power and Lossy Networks (LLNs) [1]. Designed to address the needs of resource-constrained environments, RPL plays a crucial role in IoT applications, including smart homes, agriculture, and industrial automation.

However, due to its initial design priorities, security was treated as a secondary concern, leaving RPL vulnerable to numerous routing attacks. Attacks such as Rank, Sybil, Blackhole, and Wormhole exploit weaknesses in RPL's core security mechanisms, leading to performance degradation and threats to data reliability [2]. The growing prevalence of these threats underscores the urgent need for advanced protection mechanisms. Machine learning and deep learning algorithms have recently garnered attention as promising tools for detecting and mitigating these threats. Among these, Hello Flood and Blackhole attacks significantly impact both network traffic and power consumption, posing serious risks to IoT systems and demanding effective detection solutions [3].

This study investigates the impact of Hello Flood and Blackhole attacks on power consumption and network traffic in RPL-based IoT networks. It proposes a machine learning and deep learning-based approach for the early detection of these conditions. To emulate RPL networks and simulate the attacks described above, the Cooja simulator, based on the Contiki operating system, is employed. Wireshark and "Foren6" are used to monitor network traffic, enabling a comparative analysis between reference and attack scenarios.

The analyses reveal the severe effects of Hello Flood and Blackhole attacks on IoT networks in detail. Moreover, the performance of various machine learning and deep learning algorithms in detecting these attacks is evaluated. The findings of this study provide a valuable reference for enhancing the security of RPL-based IoT systems and for building more resilient infrastructures against such threats [4].

2 RELATED WORK

The Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged as a transformative paradigm, enabling the interconnection of physical devices across a broad spectrum of applications, from individual lifestyle practices to industrial operations. The IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks (RPL) is widely used in IoT applications as a core routing protocol designed specifically for low-power and lossy networks (LLNs). Kharrufa et al. (2019) highlighted that RPL was standardized by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) in 2012 to provide optimized solutions for the constrained capabilities of IoT devices [5]. However, Raoof et al. (2018) emphasized that RPL offers only basic-level protection against routing attacks such as Rank, Sybil, Blackhole, and Wormhole, calling for comprehensive systematic investigations [6].

Airehrour et al. (2019) drew attention to the lack of security emphasis during RPL's initial design stages and developed a trust-based mechanism called SecTrust-RPL to mitigate vulnerabilities [7]. Boudouaia et al. pointed out that Rank attacks, which manipulate network topology, were first identified around 2013 and have since gained increasing significance in the literature [8]. Wormhole attacks were similarly explored in both theoretical and practical contexts around the same period. Goyal and Dutta [9] contributed to raising awareness on this issue, while Perazzo et al. provided an in-depth analysis of the challenges posed by Wormhole attacks in RPL-based networks [10].

Since 2015, machine learning and deep learning-based security solutions have gained significant traction in the research literature on RPL. Al-Amiedy et al. [3, 11] underlined the transformative impact of these approaches on RPL security, noting their potential to bring a paradigm shift in the field. Violettas et al. [12] developed software-based IDS systems to enhance the detection of RPL-related attacks. Berguiga et al. [13] proposed hybrid deep learning-based intrusion detection systems (IDS) for RPL-based networks in medical IoT applications, achieving high accuracy rates. In the industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) domain, Karacayılmaz and Artuner designed AI-based mechanisms for attack detection and prevention, offering solutions tailored to industrial security requirements [14].

Recent research has also focused on lightweight and autonomous systems. Verma and Ranga proposed lightweight IDS models for low-power RPL networks [15], while Osman et al. [16] introduced a framework that successfully detects multiple attack types using genetic algorithm-based

feature selection. Similarly, Al Sawafi et al. [17] achieved high accuracy in the simultaneous detection of multiple threats using hybrid deep learning-based systems. Cakir et al. [18] effectively implemented a GRU-based deep learning model for attack detection and prevention in RPL networks.

Contemporary literature also includes more detailed analyses of specific security threats and targeted solutions. Bang and Rao [19] introduced the EMBOF-RPL method for early detection of Rank attacks. Murali and Jamalipour [20] developed lightweight IDS solutions to counter Sybil attacks in mobile RPL contexts. Farzaneh et al. [21] demonstrated that anomaly-based IDS systems yield effective results in attack detection within RPL-based IoT networks.

Overall, the body of work on RPL-based IoT security has seen significant progress, with a wide range of comprehensive solutions proposed to address emerging security demands. The depth and diversity of existing research underscore the need for flexible and efficient security mechanisms that are tailored to the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of IoT systems.

What sets our work apart is the integration of machine learning and deep learning models into a comparative and performance-driven detection framework for RPL-based IoT networks, with a particular focus on the Hello Flood and Blackhole attacks. Unlike prior studies, our research not only simulates real-world attack scenarios using Contiki and Cooja but also conducts extensive traffic analysis with Wireshark and Foren6, yielding empirical insights. Moreover, by evaluating both energy consumption and classification performance metrics, we propose a dual-focused security assessment strategy that balances accuracy with real-time applicability, providing a novel reference point for future IoT network protection architectures.

3 METHOD

Within the scope of this study, the implementation and evaluation of the simulated attacks were conducted using the Contiki operating system, employing the Cooja simulator and the Foren6 network analysis tool. The network model created in the simulation environment consists of a central communication node (mote), 50 standard nodes (motes), and one attacker node (also a mote). In this configuration, the primary function of the standard nodes is to transmit data to external networks via the central node.

In the Hello flood attack scenario, the primary function of the attacker node is to continuously and intensively broadcast hello packets, thereby increasing the energy consumption of the standard and central nodes and disrupting their everyday operations. This attack is carried out by placing the attacker node within the communication range of the central node. Upon receiving the incessant hello packets, the standard nodes respond by sending reply packets back to the attacker node, resulting in an uncontrolled increase in communication traffic. As a result, regular network operation is disrupted, the energy resources of the standard nodes are quickly depleted, and the overall network functionality deteriorates.

In the Blackhole attack scenario, the attacker node adopts a different method by deliberately discarding packets sent by other nodes in the network, thereby disrupting network traffic. Located within the coverage area of the central node, the attacker node intentionally drops all data packets routed to it. This results in a significant interruption of the network's data flow, severely compromising communication reliability and overall network performance.

In both attack scenarios, all nodes in the network continue to communicate using regular data packets under normal operating conditions. Wireshark software was used to monitor, record, and comprehensively analyze the inter-node communication traffic in the simulated scenarios. The data obtained through Wireshark objectively and thoroughly reveals the impact of the attacks on network performance. These detailed analyses provide a significant foundation for assessing the effects of the attacks.

Figure 1: System Flowchart

The flow diagram presented in Figure 1 outlines the implementation and detection of Blackhole and Hello Flood attacks in RPL-based IoT networks, which are addressed through three main phases: the Discovery Phase, the Attack Phase, and the Attack Detection Phase. This process systematically encompasses the steps of analyzing the network, executing the attack, and detecting and mitigating threats.

3.1 Discovery Phase

The initial step of the attack scenario, the Discovery Phase, focuses on systematically scanning the network structure and identifying potential target nodes. During this phase, passive or active scanning techniques are employed to explore the network and detect the presence of nodes. If no nodes are identified, the process is terminated. However, if one or more nodes are detected, a deeper analysis is carried out.

Detailed information, such as the brand, model, hardware type, and other identifying features of the detected nodes, is collected, and the communication traffic of these nodes is monitored over a specified period. This enables a comprehensive understanding of the network topology, communication intensity, and potential vulnerabilities. The gathered information serves as a fundamental data source for shaping the attack strategy and selecting target nodes in subsequent phases.

3.2 Attack Phase

The second phase of the study, the Attack Phase, involves the controlled initiation of Blackhole and Hello Flood attacks targeting the nodes identified during the discovery process. In this phase, the attacker node is activated per predefined attack scenarios, and various protocol exploitation mechanisms are deployed against the target nodes.

First, the effectiveness of the Blackhole attack is assessed. The study examines whether the attacker node disrupts the routing process, causing data transmission to cease. If the attacker is found

to drop packets passing through the target node, thereby interrupting network traffic, the attack is deemed successful, and the system proceeds to the next stage.

Next, the impact of the Hello Flood attack is analyzed. In this context, the attacker node sends a high volume of fake "Hello" messages, and the target node is evaluated for signs of abnormal power consumption. If a significant increase in energy usage is observed in the target node, the attack is considered adequate and is dynamically continued on new target nodes. Otherwise, if no notable increase in power consumption is detected, the attack process is halted, and the analysis concludes.

This phase follows a cyclic structure aimed at maximizing the impact of the attacks on the network. Additionally, dynamic target-switching mechanisms allow the attack to propagate through different sections of the network, playing a critical role in evaluating the system's resilience.

3.3 Attack Detection Phase:

The third and final phase, the Attack Detection Phase, focuses on identifying and classifying security threats within the network environment. In this phase, the communication traffic of the target node is closely monitored, and relevant packets are systematically recorded. The raw data obtained is then subjected to a comprehensive analysis using machine learning and deep learning algorithms.

This analysis facilitates the identification of weak points in the network topology and the detection of anomalous behaviors, playing a crucial role in uncovering potential attacks. Special emphasis is placed on routing protocol attacks, particularly Hello Flood and Blackhole attacks, which are classified by matching their behavioral characteristics with the collected traffic data.

The attack model developed in this context not only enables accurate identification of existing threats but also contributes to the development of preventive security mechanisms against future attack scenarios. This phase is regarded as a strategic component for enhancing network security and constitutes one of the core outcomes of the study.

4 ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

In this section, the impacts of HelloFlood and Blackhole attacks on power consumption and network traffic in wireless sensor networks are systematically analyzed. The evaluations were carried out using Foren6 and Wireshark tools in comparison with reference scenarios, and the resulting findings are presented in detail.

4.1 HelloFlood Attack Analysis

Figure 2: The effect of the HelloFlood attack on power consumption

The effect of the HelloFlood attack on power consumption is clearly illustrated in Figure 2. In this attack type, the attacker node continuously sends "Hello" messages, which increases the packet reception (RX) operations on the target nodes, leading to a significant rise in total energy

consumption. When compared to the reference scenario (Figure 2), it was observed that energy consumption levels rose from approximately 20% to around 50–60% during the attack. This increase had a severe impact on the network's energy efficiency, significantly reducing the operational lifespan of the nodes. Additionally, the destructive impact of the HelloFlood attack on overall network performance became evident through increased traffic load and performance degradation.

4.2 Blackhole Attack Analysis

Figure 3: The impact of the Blackhole attack on energy consumption

The impact of the Blackhole attack on energy consumption is visualized in Figure 3. In this type of attack, the attacker node manipulates routing tables to draw traffic towards itself and then discards the packets without forwarding them to the intended destination. During this process, packet transmission (TX) operations on the target nodes increased, while the rate of successful communication notably decreased. Compared to the reference case, a significant increase was observed in the energy consumption of the ON state and TX components. This indicates that the Blackhole attack negatively affects communication efficiency and leads to unnecessary depletion of energy resources. Moreover, the disruption in data transmission caused by the attack severely compromises network reliability.

4.3 Network Analysis with Wireshark and Foren6

Figure 4: The traffic analysis carried out via Wireshark.

To better understand the effects of both attack types on the network, detailed analyses were conducted using Wireshark and Foren6 tools. The traffic analysis carried out via Wireshark is presented in Figure 4. During the HelloFlood attack, a dramatic increase in the number of packets across the network was observed, indicating a substantial rise in traffic load and a significant drop in

performance. In the Blackhole attack scenario, it was determined that the traffic routed to the attacker node was not forwarded, effectively “swallowing” the packets. This result demonstrates that even though the number of packets sent by the target nodes increased, those packets did not reach the recipient nodes.

Figure 5: The analyses conducted using the Foren6 tool.

The analyses conducted using the Foren6 tool are summarized in Figure 5. These analyses reveal routing table modifications and topological disruptions in the network during attack scenarios. In the HelloFlood scenario, many nodes were observed attempting to route through the attacker node, which negatively impacted overall network performance. In the Blackhole scenario, severe data loss occurred as the attacker node attracted data flow but failed to transmit it further.

4.4 Evaluation of the Findings

The conducted analyses demonstrate the negative impacts of HelloFlood and Blackhole attacks on IoT-based wireless sensor networks. The HelloFlood attack significantly increases energy consumption and critically shortens the operational time of the nodes. The Blackhole attack causes interruptions in data transmission and seriously threatens network reliability. In this context, the findings underscore the crucial importance of early attack detection and the implementation of proactive security measures. It is evident that ensuring the security of IoT systems requires continuous monitoring of network traffic and the rapid detection of anomalies.

5 ATTACK ANALYSIS USING MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING

In this study, the performance of various machine learning and deep learning algorithms was systematically evaluated for the rapid and accurate detection of cyberattacks in Internet of Things (IoT) systems. The focus was placed on detecting HelloFlood and Blackhole attacks, and the effectiveness of the analysis methods was examined in detail based on experimental data. The primary goal of the attack detection process is to identify threats at the earliest possible stage, thereby preventing damage to the network.

The dataset used for attack detection includes both benign network traffic and traffic data generated during HelloFlood and Blackhole attacks. In the experimental analyses, a comprehensive performance comparison was conducted using the LightGBM, XGBoost (XGB), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) algorithms. This comparison enabled the evaluation of algorithms in terms of classification accuracy, speed, and other performance metrics.

Table 1: Performance Comparison of Models

Model	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall	AUC	Training Time(s)	Test Time(s)
BiLSTM	0.9902	0.9885	0.9889	0.9891	0.9983	390.76	8.94
LSTM	0.9812	0.9768	0.9775	0.9783	0.9941	244.50	7.22
XGBoost	0.9788	0.9784	0.9779	0.9789	0.9925	100.35	1.21
LightGBM	0.9656	0.9668	0.9680	0.9657	0.9865	21.06	5.45

The experimental findings are summarized in the Performance Comparison of Models graph presented in Table 1. According to the results, the BiLSTM algorithm demonstrated the highest overall performance, achieving an accuracy rate of 99.02%. As also shown in the same graph, the BiLSTM model demonstrated clear superiority over other algorithms in terms of F1 score (98.85%), Precision (98.89%), Recall (98.91%), and AUC (99.83%). However, the training time for the BiLSTM model was measured at 390.76 seconds, which is considerably longer than the other models. In contrast, the XGB algorithm offered the fastest performance in terms of testing time, completing the test in just 1.21 seconds, as shown in Figure 6, providing a critical advantage in cybersecurity scenarios that require urgent responses.

Table 1 Confision Matrices

The analysis of the confusion matrices was carried out in detail using the Confusion Matrices graph shown in Table 2. This analysis revealed that the BiLSTM algorithm minimized classification errors and accurately distinguished between different classes, including benign traffic, HelloFlood, and Blackhole attacks. It was observed that misclassifications were kept at a very low level, and the system could accurately detect each type of attack at an early stage. On the other hand, while the XGB algorithm provided faster classification due to its shorter testing time, it lagged behind BiLSTM in terms of classification accuracy.

In this context, for cybersecurity scenarios where both accuracy and testing time are critical for securing IoT networks, the advantages of different algorithms should be evaluated based on system requirements. While BiLSTM stands out with its high accuracy and detailed analysis capabilities, particularly in the metrics indicated in Table 1, XGB offers a significant advantage with its fast-testing time, as also shown in the same graph, in scenarios where early detection of attacks is crucial.

6 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The experimental results reveal that both HelloFlood and Blackhole attacks have a significant adverse impact on RPL-based IoT networks, affecting energy consumption, communication reliability, and overall network performance. In the HelloFlood scenario, the continuous transmission of fake "Hello" messages by the attacker node resulted in a drastic increase in energy consumption, rising from baseline levels of 20% to over 50–60%. This increase directly affected node lifespan and disrupted network performance due to the excessive RX operations and increased traffic congestion.

In the Blackhole scenario, although RX activity was lower than in HelloFlood, the attacker node intercepted and discarded packets, resulting in a notable rise in TX power consumption and substantial packet loss. This behavior critically compromised communication reliability, as evidenced by the reduced delivery ratio and increased retransmissions.

Machine learning and deep learning models were employed to detect these attacks using traffic datasets generated under both normal and attack conditions. Among the tested models—LightGBM, XGBoost, LSTM, and BiLSTM—the BiLSTM model achieved the highest performance, with an accuracy of 99.02% and an AUC of 99.83%, effectively distinguishing between benign traffic and the two attack types. However, the BiLSTM model's training time was substantially higher than others, highlighting a trade-off between accuracy and computational cost.

Conversely, the XGBoost algorithm achieved the fastest testing time (1.21 seconds), making it well-suited for real-time applications where immediate response is critical, albeit at the cost of slightly lower classification metrics. These findings underscore the importance of selecting models based on specific deployment requirements—balancing accuracy, latency, and resource constraints.

Overall, the results demonstrate that a dual approach, integrating both protocol-level monitoring (via tools such as Wireshark and Foren6) and intelligent detection systems (via ML/DL models), provides a robust framework for early threat detection and mitigation in IoT networks.

7 CONCLUSION

In this study, the effects of two prevalent cyberattacks—HelloFlood and Blackhole—on IoT-based wireless sensor networks were systematically analyzed. The findings revealed that both attacks cause significant disruption to network performance and lead to substantial increases in node power consumption. The HelloFlood attack, by generating intense fake packet traffic, elevated the energy consumption of the nodes and degraded overall performance. In contrast, the Blackhole attack posed a severe threat to network reliability by deliberately intercepting and discarding data packets, thus interrupting normal routing operations.

In the machine learning and deep learning-based detection analyses, the Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) algorithm achieved the highest accuracy rate (99.02%). It outperformed other models in terms of F1 score (98.85%), Precision (98.89%), Recall (98.91%), and AUC (99.83%). However, its training time (390.76 seconds) was significantly longer than that of the other algorithms. Conversely, XGBoost (XGB) achieved the fastest testing time at just 1.21 seconds, providing a critical advantage for real-time cybersecurity scenarios where rapid threat detection is crucial for preserving network integrity.

In conclusion, the development of effective attack detection and mitigation mechanisms is essential to ensuring the security of IoT networks. This study highlights the potential of combining models like BiLSTM and XGB by balancing accuracy and response time, thereby providing a strategic foundation for future security applications in resource-constrained and mission-critical IoT environments.

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